

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_3_2_5	
Title	<i>Padlet</i>
Category	Socio-cultural (for Eidsvika)
Purpose of the method	<i>Padlet is an interactive community tool. We will use it as a public/shared gallery. People who take walks on Eidsvika will find QR codes on small signs where they can access the gallery and upload a picture from their trip. The purpose is to create a stronger sense of community, low-threshold engagement and to collect data by “counting” the recreational use of it.</i>
Effort in time	<i>The padlet was created within 5 hours and so was the design of the signs.</i>
Number of objects investigated	<i>N/A.</i>
Data format	<i>textual, images, numerical</i>
Description	<p><i>Padlet is a low-threshold, interactive community tool working with creative pin-walls, that is widely used in education settings. It does not require downloading an app or creating an user-account. People who receive the link (though a QR code on signs in the nature area in our case) are able to contribute. Our pin-wall is a gallery. The setting of the gallery only allows the upload of pictures taken by the camera immediately (not from camera roll). This will help to create a clearer picture of “reported” recreational use by the community. It is also possible to give the pictures a title. Posts can be made anonymous.</i></p> <p><i>We established the tool because we observed that many community members upload pictures from their hikes in the area in the large facebook group. However, this is a politically loaded place and members usually post with their clear name and they have to have a facebook account. By making the gallery we hope to establish a distinct space for impressions of the area and make it even easier to upload pictures for everyone. This will help the community to feel ownership of the area and the research team to have data in the form of numbers and images about the recreational use.</i></p>
Basic Literature	<p><i>What is Padlet? Padlet.Help.</i> https://padlet.help/l/en/article/cpfiutfzsb-what-is-padlet</p>
Contact person within the project	<i>Selina Rombach, selina.rombach@uib.no, Research assistant case study Bergen</i>